

Abstract. This article discusses the theoretical foundations of human resource development in tourism, the stages of human resource development, and their individual features. The article also analyzes the institutional framework for the development of human resources, reforms aimed at improving the skills of personnel in the tourism sector, and relevant indicators.

Keywords: Human resources, human resource management, human resource development (HRD), tourism industry, human capital development (HCD), education, training and development (T&D) in tourism, tourism industry.

Introduction

The tourism sector is becoming a strategically important type of business that is rapidly developing in the country's economy. In tourism, the staff and especially the guides are the most important factors for the success of the trip. The modern development of tourism and hospitality is based on the potential of natural, socio-economic, cultural, historical and, of course, human resources. No other resource, no artificial intelligence, can replace employees in the tourism industry. Therefore, the main resource of tourism development will always be people and their skills.

Therefore, the Presidential Decree No. 300 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 11, 2023 on the "Uzbekistan-2030" strategy "Increasing the number of tourists by creating broad conditions for the development of foreign and domestic tourism in Uzbekistan" the following tasks are defined in the direction of the 58th goal "Rapid development of the tourism sector and infrastructure":

- Diversification of types of tourism, including the development of a program for the development of MICE-tourism, rural tourism, bicycle tourism, agro-tourism, mountain tourism, children's and youth tourism in the regions, participation in international tourism exhibitions and fairs organized in foreign countries. Wide promotion of Uzbekistan's tourism potential;
- organizing press tours around the country for leading international publications, TV channels, famous bloggers;
- holding "Road show" and "B2B" meetings abroad in cooperation with local tour operators and transport organizations.

In order to ensure the implementation of activities and tasks, the specified measure shows the need to develop not only laws and decisions in the field of tourism, but also the development of innovative capabilities, knowledge, qualifications and skills of employees operating in the field [1].

Literature review

In the field of tourism, many scientific studies have been conducted on the management of human resources, the development of human resources, in particular, the development of human resources based on HR technologies.

Central Asia also made a significant contribution to the development of tourism, and during this period, the great leader Amir Temur's kingdom was also very important. At that time, the state of Amir Temur established almost all the countries on the known land. It was during the time of Amir Temur that the status of the "Great Silk Road" was raised, which led to the development of cultural relations between states and peoples.

The term "human resource management" was first used in science and management practice in the USA and Great Britain since 1970, and then in other countries with developed market

economies. This is, first of all, a rethinking of the role and place of man in economic activity during the scientific and technical revolution, and he is not only a "live" factor of production, but also a personality with his own interests, motivation, psychology, personnel, entrepreneurship, etc. is also related to being treated as [2].

The first concepts of human resource development (HRD) in foreign practice date back to the early 1980s. Economists I.A.Esaulova and A.Haslinda said that "human resource" is a stable resource that can withstand external changes, that "human resource" is an important asset in increasing efficiency and implementing strategic plans of the company. pointed out [3].

If we refer to more specific years, the concept was first developed in the West in 1803 by Robert Owen, who emphasized the human needs of workers. He taught how to clean and improve the workplace. He emphasized the need for social activities to increase the efficiency of workers [4].

N.Malcom and N.Leonar human resources emphasized content-based and experiential and human-oriented education instead of only didactic learning. N.Leonar studied more the difference between "human resource management" and "human resource development" [5].

The concept of HRD was officially introduced by L.Nadler in 1969 at a conference organized by the American Society for Education and Development. L. Nadler defines "Human resource development as a learning experience organized for a certain period of time and designed to create an opportunity to change behavior" [6].

According to Indian scientist S.R.Pulapa, HRD from an organizational point of view is a process of helping and encouraging the employees of the organization to acquire and develop technical, managerial and behavioral knowledge and skills, forming the necessary values, beliefs and attitudes. In addition, in order to positively contribute to organizational, group, individual and social goals, enterprises are encouraged to fulfill current and future roles by realizing human potential [7].

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In particular, according to Academician K.Kh.Abdurakhmanov, the advantages of human resources are determined as follows:

- level of training of human resources (level of education and qualification, broad and narrow specialization);
- creative ability;
- striving to increase personal potential;
- labor activity;
- the main driving force of social production;
- the object of the most effective capital investment is to serve the improvement of knowledge and skills, which will bring the highest effect in the future.

Scientist K.Kh.Abdurahmanov, while highlighting the advantages of human resources, defined the concept of "human resource" as follows. Human resources are the part of the country's population that has physical development, mental abilities and knowledge necessary for useful activities [8].

According to the definition of R.Swanson and D.Arnold: "The goals of human resources development should be related to the strategic goals of the organization, because the subjects of human resources development are the top and middle managers of the company who set these strategic goals employees" [9].

According to J.Walton, "the development of the organization is inextricably linked with the development of its structure, values, behavior, mutual relations and professional qualities of its employees" [10].

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Training is the main way to develop human resources. Defined Human Resource Development (HRD) as "the process of developing the human experience through organizational development and employee training and development to improve performance." The concept of HRD is the process of acquiring skills, self-awareness and modernization, which can be implemented through short and long-term training programs [11].

HRD scholars often focus on on-the-job training and development of employees, with the direct impact of employee education, lifelong learning, and individual learning on workplace outcomes. they insist that it will show a secret. Also, training and development of employees allows to eliminate problems in the workplace and increase labor efficiency [12].

According to Prof. T.V.Rao, India's most renowned expert on HRD, Human Resource Development (HRD) is the continuous and planned support to the employees of an organization to perform various functions relevant to the present era. To acquire or strengthen the abilities, to discover their internal capabilities and to develop their overall capabilities in order to fully use them is a process covered by the goals of personal and organizational development [13].

The beginning of targeted personnel training activities is connected with the period of mass production of machines in the mid-30s of the 20th century and the formation of the scientific management school, which laid the foundation for internal personnel training methodology. The concept of organizational development expresses the need for the organization to have constant opportunities for training and development of personnel. However, by the end of the 1950s, the "human element" of organizational development came to the fore, and the idea was put forward that employee development directly affects the labor efficiency of the enterprise. However, for a long time, the employee was accepted only as the owner of the ability to perform the functions assigned to him, and the purpose of internal training was to adjust his professional qualities to the requirements of the workplace [14].

A significant change in the methodology of human resource development (HRD) can be associated with the stage of transition from industrial to post-industrial economy, in which deep structural changes have begun in industrialized countries, the balance between industrial production and the service sector has changed. "changed in favor of showing. high-tech production appeared, and as a result, the share of highly skilled labor force increased sharply. According to J.Mathew, the concept of human resources development (HRD) is an organizational working environment designed to mitigate conflicts between different approaches, to achieve harmonious labor relations in the conditions of constant changes between the needs of the employee and the company [15].

A.L.Poltarykhin in his research put forward the opinion that "the information-technological revolution in the industrial economy and the subsequent transition to the knowledge economy not only led to the filling of labor with intellectual components, but also changed the nature of competition between organizations." This gave a person's creative abilities, his professional skills the opportunity to create new knowledge and apply them in practice in new products, technologies, skills and new relationships with consumers [16].

Employee development is the growth and development of the employee's personal abilities, taking into account changes not related to current or future work in enterprises [17].

Our scientific research is distinguished by the fact that the management and development of human resources in tourism are significantly different from other resources, and therefore they require special management methods.

Research methodology

In this study, empirical and conceptual studies related to the issues of human resources development in the field of tourism were studied on the basis of HR technologies reflected in a number of scientific sources, and the scientific approaches in them were systematized. Also, systematic analysis, logic, induction and deduction, analysis and synthesis, comparative analysis, monographic analysis and grouping methods were used in the research work.

Analysis and results

On the other hand, we should say that in recent years, the improvement of the standard of living of the population, the increase of people's income, and their desire to live well, the demand for using quality services is increasing. At the same time, the situation shows that the quality of services provided in the field of tourism depends on the knowledge and skills of the employees working in it, and that these processes are an urgent task that cannot be postponed.

It is in this respect that the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 18.07.2024 No. PQ-269 on retraining and upgrading the skills of personnel in the field of tourism was adopted in our country, and according to the decision, the continuous education system in the field of tourism is being further improved in line with international standards. In accordance with the modern requirements of the labor market, a system of training of highly qualified competitive personnel has been established, and a number of measures have been defined to ensure the integration of science, education and production:

Starting from the 2024/2025 academic year, the system of personnel training in the fields of tourism and hotel management will be launched in state higher education institutions on the basis of three-year higher education programs. The educational process is organized in the form of dual education based on the "block-module" system. In this case, the share of theoretical and practical training of educational processes:

In the first stage - 80% theoretical and 20% practical.

In the second stage - 50% theoretical and 50% practical.

In the third stage - 30% theoretical and 70% practical.

From August 1, 2024, in order to carry out the educational process together with practice in higher education institutions training personnel in the field of tourism, practice bases that do not have the status of a legal entity (tour operator, tour agent, tour guide-interpreter) will be established in their territories at the expense of extra-budgetary funds. , hotel and tourism transport service facilities) are allowed to be organized in the prescribed manner [18].

Table 1**Employees who worked in the field of tourism in Uzbekistan dynamics**

Indicators	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	The difference between 2016 and 2023 (-, +)
Total (without deputy employees)	1945	2061	2486	2920	2330	1956	2793	3490	1545
higher education	1182	1223	1295	1595	1229	1048	1285	1862	680
including vocational tourism education	278	310	304	404	249	246	256	379	101
medium special education	657	729	790	1175	935	716	1345	1344	687
including vocational	84	91	110	134	88	72	125	122	38

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tourism education									
deputy employees	234	51	280	313	157	158	342	387	153
managers	599	551	599	691	588	475	794	1008	409
guides and translators	134	128	143	238	141	129	180	246	112

According to employment data for 2019-2023, it is about 210,000 jobs on average. It is worth noting that the main sectors in the dynamics of employees' activity in the tourism sector are "food and beverage service", in which 62,898 people are employed; there are 56,430 jobs in the "passenger vehicle transport" sector; "accommodation services" - 51,955 employees, "sports and recreation" - 16,236 employees; "cultural services" - from 2019 to 2021, an average of 11,693 people worked.

In recent years, we can notice that the number of highly educated employees, those who have received tourism education, managers, guides and translators, tour operators in the field of tourism in our country is increasing and has a positive effect on the services provided in the field. According to Table 1, the total number of employees working in the industry increased to 1,545 from 2016 to 2023. It is noteworthy that the number of employees with higher education has increased to 680. In 2016, there were 599 managers, and in 2023, their number increased to 409. We believe that it is necessary to improve the skills of employees in the field of tourism not only in terms of quantity, but also in terms of quality.

Conclusions and suggestions

Analyzing the views, definitions and approaches of economists on the development of human resources in the field of tourism, we make the following suggestions for the development of human resources in our country, drawing conclusions from the reforms carried out in the field of human resources development in our country:

First of all, it is suggested to develop the emotional intelligence of employees in the field, taking into account that the development of human resources is a very important resource in the field of tourism, unlike other fields;

Secondly, in the development of employees working in the field of tourism, whether they are managers, tour operators, guides and translators, or tour guides, educational programs should train employees who can describe the national color of tourism and express the uniqueness of the region. it is necessary to achieve training and development;

Thirdly, taking into account that the whole world is digitizing, it is appropriate to develop the digital skills of all types of employees in the field of tourism;

Fourthly, it is possible to expand the geography of sales and the number of sales by developing the skills of online advertising and sales of online services of tourism marketers.

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